

Evaluation of GSM and GPRS Systems in Emergency Telemedicine

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Abstract. Emerging technologies in wireless and mobile telecommunication networks, combined with the simultaneous rapid advances in information technology, are leading to many new solutions in the field of telemedicine. As a result the opportunities for improving further existing and supporting new advanced services for healthcare are widened. The objective of this study is to carry out a practical evaluation of the performance of the GSM and GPRS systems in the transmission/reception of images and video as well as Patient Record and biosignals in emergency cases. The data transfer rate achieved with GPRS were in the range of 32 Kbps (while for GSM 9.6 kbps) with the download time for typical images of a file size of 200 Kbytes to the mobile device to be in the region of 60 seconds. Similar performance was also recorded in the case of a moving station (simulating the ambulance). In conclusion, the physicians were very pleased by the benefits offered by the system through the freedom of access, anywhere and anytime even in motion.

1. Introduction

Telemedicine can be defined as the distant delivery of health care and remote sharing of medical knowledge using telecommunication means. In recent years, several telemedicine applications have been successfully implemented over wired and wireless communication technologies [1]. However, nowadays, modern wireless telecommunication means like GSM and GPRS and the forthcoming UMTS (Universal Mobile Telephone System) mobile telephony standards allow the operation of wireless telemedicine systems freeing the medical personnel and/or the patient from fixed locations [1]-[4]. The objective of this paper is to carry out a practical evaluation of the performance of the GSM and GPRS systems in the transmission/reception of medical images and video as well as patient record and ECG in emergency cases.

1.1 The GSM and GPRS systems

The main wireless technologies that are being used in wireless telemedicine systems are the GSM, GPRS, satellite, Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN) and Bluetooth. GSM provides data transfer speeds of up to 9.6 Kbps or up to 43.3 Kbps when HSCSD (High Speed Circuit Switched Data) is used. The theoretical maximum downlink data rate for GPRS is 171.2 kbps (assuming coding scheme 4 and are simultaneous utilization of eight timeslots). Today, however, GPRS coding is limited to scheme 2 and utilization of only four timeslots at most, giving a maximum throughput of around 45 kbps (under ideal radio conditions). The evolution of mobile telecommunication systems from 2G to 2.5G and subsequently to 3G technologies will enable faster data transfer rates thus facilitating the development of telemedicine systems that require high bandwidth.

Fig.1. Infrastructure of an emergency telemedicine network

1.2 Patient record, Medical images, ECG data

During emergency medical cases the existence of information such patients' medical record can be proved to be essential, especially when dealing with patients that have chronic diseases or drug allergies. Such information has only the size of some Kilobytes and can be transmitted easily over most wireless communication means. In addition modern Ambulance vehicles, which are equipped as Mobile Intensive Care Units (MICU), might carry portable imaging devices such as portable X-Rays. Images produced from these devices have the size of some Megabytes depending on image resolution colors etc. Because of their size, the transmission of such files over wireless communication means might not be feasible in a logical period of time. Furthermore MICU Ambulance vehicles are equipped with ECG recorders. When handling difficult heart problems transmission of ECG signal from the emergency place to the place where the expert is, so as to get consultation, can be proved to be essential. In this case the size of the transmitted signals depends on several parameters, such as the number of ECG leads transmitted or the continuous transmission of ECG. For one lead ECG that will be sampled using 10 bits x 200 samples per second we get information of 2000 bits per second.

2. Materials and methods

A typical network infrastructure in support of an emergency medical system is given in Fig.1. The figure illustrates: the accident and emergency departmental server at the hospital, a rural health centre unit that is connected to the internet via ADSL and an ambulance unit or an expert physician's mobile station; connected to the internet via GSM or GPRS.

In order to start recording information based on the network presented in Fig. 1, a database was developed according to the needs of the Emergency department of the main government hospital in Cyprus (Nicosia General Hospital). Data stored in the database include all necessary information recorded during an emergency case. A sample image of the database GUI is shown on fig. 2 where on this figure information about patient's external injuries can be marked and stored in the database.

In order to start developing the complete system, the performance of the system was evaluated using wireless communication channels in the transmission of medical images of varying size by downloading images via SMTP (as email attachment) or FTP using both GSM and GPRS, and uploading images via FTP over GPRS. In addition the performance of the GPRS system using FTP access was evaluated by downloading an image file of size 180 Kbytes on a moving handheld PC at a speed of 100 km/hr.

Fig. 2. External injuries screen, Sample image from the database GUI.

3. Results

The results presented in this study were carried out using the Compaq iPAQ 3870 handheld PC equipped with the GSM/GPRS expansion pack modem with the medical images and videos varying in size between 10 Kbytes to 2 Mbytes. Figure 3 illustrates the comparison of GSM and GPRS for both SMTP and FTP protocols. It is clearly shown that for FTP the throughput performance of the GPRS is approximately triple to that of the GSM, whereas for SMTP the GPRS performance is 1.5 times to four times to that of GSM.

Fig.3. Comparison of SMTP and

Fig. 4. Download speeds for varying

FTP protocols over GSM and GPRS

file size using FTP over GPRS

Fig. 5. Upload speeds for varying file size FTP over GPRS

The corresponding download speeds for the above experiment are shown in Fig. 4 for that specific time and point. The download speed was in the region of 30 Kbps, varying between 23.5 to 34 Kbps. The performance of the system in the case of a mobile station (i.e. the case for an ambulance) traveling in a highway at 100 km/h, downloading repeatedly a 180 Kbytes image file using FTP over GPRS was very satisfactory for a significant length of the journey, with throughput values in the range of 30 to 32 Kbps. The upload of files through the GPRS system was also tested. In this case the network on which the system was tested could support only one channel for uploading files. For this reason the bit rate of transmission was similar to the GSM transmission which could go up to 9.6 Kbps. The bit rate always depends on the traffic of the network.

4. Conclusion

The results of the above experiments showed clearly that the GPRS system could be used successfully for the transmission of medical images and video employing the Tele medicine Support System. The method of downloading files using FTP over GPRS was by far superior to SMTP. As expected, the performance of GPRS is superior to that of GSM. The data transfer rates normally achieved with GPRS were in the range of 32 Kbps which is what was expected since the downlink bit rate for a 4+1 phone connection is between 5 Kbps and 40 Kbps.

The download time for typical medical images of file size 200 Kbytes to the mobile device was in the region of 60 seconds. The system was also used in an emergency scenario where a prompt second opinion was requested remotely from the specialist in the case of a serious operation. The whole teleconsultation scenario was carried out in less than five minutes. The performance of the system was also evaluated in the case of a moving station (simulating the ambulance) with satisfactory results (download speeds reaching 32 Kbps for the biggest part of the journey).

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